

**MANAGING CHILDREN'S PROBLEM BEHAVIOUR
IN EARLY CHILDHOOD CENTRES: STRATEGIES ADOPTED
BY THE EFFUTU MUNICIPALITY, GHANA**

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Abstract:

This descriptive survey sought to explore the type of children's problem behaviour and classroom management strategies adopted by the selected schools in the Effutu Municipality. The study adopted the explanatory sequential mixed method design. Data was gathered through a semi-structured interview guide and questionnaire. The stratified sampling technique was used to aid in the selection of 15 Early Childhood Centres (ECC) from three circuits within the Effutu Municipality. Simple random sampling was used to select 45 respondents from the 15 selected early childhood schools to respond to the questionnaire while purposive sampling was used to sample 15 participants who were part of the 45 questionnaire respondents to answer semi-structured interview questions designed by the researchers. Quantitative data were analysed using frequencies and percentages. Qualitative data were analysed thematically using Atlas ti software. It emerged from the findings that the predominant type of children's problem behaviour was related to aggression, non-compliance, hyperactivity, destructiveness, refusal to take instruction, intentional destruction of property, among others. It also emerged from the analysed data that the respondent used strategies such

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as doing activities in turns, teaching playground rules, verbal warning, reward and punishment, using reminders, and others as strategies to manage children's problem behaviour in their respective early childhood centres. The study recommended that Effutu Metropolitan Assembly, Winneba Educational Directorate and the headteachers of the selected schools for the study should organize programmes in collaboration with the early childhood unit on how to cope, prevent and deal with problem behaviour to ease the burden of parents and teachers.

Keywords: management, children, problem behaviour, strategies, Ghana

1. Introduction

Effective classroom management requires teachers to be skilful in their managing abilities, and not only depend on their teaching skills. Classroom management is an important accomplishment for every teacher from pre-school classrooms to the university level (Kamarulzaman & Siew, 2015). Good classroom management is like doing a surgical operation, it requires details which are involuntary layoffs and not rambling comments (Brunette, 2014). Caregivers are expected to exhibit self-discipline and good manners and not to become angry, affront the children or use blistering language on them. Their management plan is never sadist and their lives should be full of empathy, even when challenged by children to defy it (Brunette, 2014).

The early childhood years are the intensive period of child growth and development where children build foundations for the growth of future skills (Rimm Kaufman, Pianta, & Cox, 2000). Development of emotional and behavioural self-regulation and social competence are the key features of this development. The foregoing development is well recognized to the extent that children who are socially, emotionally, and behaviourally adept at the time they enter school are likely to fare better in the school environment than those who struggle with these accomplishments. It is common for young children to display low levels of problem behaviour across home, community, and school environments (Campbell, 2001). Early mastery of adequate levels of social, emotional and behavioural competencies are the indicators of the well-being of a pre-school child and are associated with future success across a variety of domains.

Conversely, early and persistent problem behaviour can affect the child's development across academic, societal, and emotional domains and put the child at risk of early academic failure (Bulotsky-Shearer & Fantuzzo, 2011; Yoleri, 2013) as well as later problems in adolescence (Dodge, Coie & Lynam, 2006). Given these risks, the main theoretical worldwide approach has been targeted at prevention of young children's challenging behaviour and early intervention for them and their families (New Freedom Commission on Mental Health, 2003; Shonkoff & Phillips, 2000).

One of the important elements of an effective manager is a teacher who is well-read on what triggers problem behaviours in children. Earlier research conducted by (Thompson, 2011) revealed that the most common children's problem behaviour is that

they do not follow directions from a teacher or caregiver. In circle time, for example, children like to talk constantly with their peers and not to listen to a teacher or health professional. Thompson further explained that children behave in such a way because they cannot understand what teachers are teaching or maybe because they do understand the words employed by teachers.

Additionally, (Martinez, 2014) identified hitting, kicking, catching, or poking other peers is common problem behaviours among children). Also, (Martinez, 2014; Morin, 2014) are of the view that children often put up certain problem behaviour to test limits and standards and to split down the precepts set out by teachers or caregivers, as well as to find out how teachers or caregivers would respond to such behaviours. The concept of problem behaviour is considered to be quite a trivial problem in its essence (Giallo & Hayes, 2007), and it is of continuing interest and concern for teachers and policymakers as well as for the community within the Effutu Municipality. It is in the light of the above researches that the researchers decided to investigate the type of children's problem behaviour prevailing in the pre-schools of the Effutu Municipality and the classroom strategies they adopt to manage those behaviours.

2. Objectives of the Study

The specific **objectives** of the study were to:

- 1) determine the type of children's problem behaviour prevailing in the pre-schools of the Effutu Municipality.
- 2) investigate classroom management strategies adopted to manage children's problem behaviour in the pre-schools of the Effutu Municipality.

2.1 Research Questions

The study seeks to answer the following questions:

- 1) What are the types of children's problem behaviour prevailing in the pre-schools of the Effutu Municipality?
- 2) What classroom management strategies are adopted to manage children's problem behaviour in the pre-schools of the Effutu Municipality?

2.2 Significance of the Study

This study is intended to inform teacher education institutions about children's problem behaviour and encourage them to incorporate classroom management strategies in teacher education curricula and to let them know the need for children teachers' knowledge in classroom management. The study will also bring to bear on teachers the need to understand widespread problem behaviours and how it relates to the teaching-learning process. This will provide teachers and policymakers as well as the community with information on classroom management task consisting of planning lessons, providing a conducive learning environment, teaching children and the most daunting task of all, is appropriately responding to children's behavioural problems.

Empirical evidence that results from exploring children's problem behaviour and classroom management strategies will encourage researchers to ascertain the factors that influence the development of problem behaviour to evaluate, identify, and examine effective classroom management techniques to improve practices.

3. Methodology

The study adopted the explanatory sequential mixed method approach to facilitate the achievement of the stated objectives of the study. Creswell (2014) points out those sequential mixed method procedures are those in which the researcher seeks to elaborate on or expand on the findings of one method with another method.

The overall intent for this design was to have the qualitative data help explain in more details the initial quantitative results.

3.1 Population of the Study

The kindergarten teachers of Basic public and preparatory schools in the Effutu Municipality in Ghana formed the population of this study.

3.2 Sample and Sampling Techniques

The study employed stratified sampling, simple random sampling and purposive sampling as a means to get the required sample for the study. Specifically, the sample size for the study was 60 comprising 45 females and 15 males kindergarten teachers. This sample size was selected from 15 schools drawn from three circuits within the Effutu Municipality. Stratified sampling technique was used to aid in the selection of the 15 schools. Simple random sampling was used to select 45 respondents from the 15 selected schools to respond to the questionnaire while purposive sampling was used to sample 15 participants who were part of the 45 questionnaire respondents to answer semi-structured interview questions designed by the researchers.

3.3 Instruments

A questionnaire developed by the researchers was used to gather the relevant data for the study. Specifically, Likert scale questionnaire with options presented in a four-point scale ranging from: Strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and strongly Disagree (SA) respectively was designed to capture a range of responses. Correspondingly each of those options was rated the following: SA (4), A (3), D (2) and SA (1). For clarity 'Strongly Agree' and 'Agree' were combined as 'Agree' likewise 'Disagree' or 'Strongly Disagree' were treated as 'Disagree'. The questionnaire items were generated from the data collected and analyzed from the qualitative phase.

3.4 Procedure for Data Collection

Permission was sought from the appropriate District Educational Office and the school authorities to enable the researcher to conduct the study.

The consent of the respondents was sort after which respondents were given two days to answer the questionnaires to the best of their knowledge. The purpose of the study was explained to the respondents; the various difficulties of the respondents were rectified by the researcher. The researchers interviewed the respondents for about 40 minutes. A Samsung Tablet 2.0 was used to record the interview between the respondents and the researcher. The data was then played and transcribed for analysis. The returned rate for the questionnaire administered was 100%.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

Percentages and frequencies were used as statistical tools to analyse the quantitative data while a Samsung Tablet 2.0 was used to record the interview and transcribed.

3.6 Presentation of Quantitative and Qualitative Data

This section presents quantitative and qualitative data collected from the field in an attempt to achieve the stated research objectives.

Research Question 1: What are the types of children's problem behaviour prevailing in the selected pre-schools in the Effutu Municipality?

The items elicited responses on the types of children's problem behaviour prevailing in the selected pre-schools in the Effutu Municipality Result of this investigation is presented in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Types of Children's Problem Behaviour

Items	Agree		Disagree	
	F	(%)	F	(%)
Children exhibit various problem behaviour in the early childhood centre	36	80	9	20
Aggression is a common problem behaviour among pre-schoolers.	33	73.3	12	26.7
Non-compliance is a problem behaviour among pre-schoolers	34	75.6	11	24.4
Hyperactivity is a problem behaviour in pre-school centres.	38	84.4	7	15.6
Destructiveness is a prevailing condition among children in the pre-school centres	33	73.3	12	26.3

Source: Field data (2018).

Table 1 shows a description of the response relating to the views of teachers on the various types of children's problem behaviour. The majority of the respondents 36(80%) agreed that children exhibit various problem behaviour in the early childhood centre. With regards to aggression 33(73%) of the respondents agreed that it is a common problem behaviour among the pre-schoolers. This finding is in line with what is indicated in the literature. Both Martinez(2014)and Goddard(2010) identified that aggressive behaviour displayed by children is a growing and common problem of concern. Martinez further explained that hitting, kicking, catching, or poking other peers as common problem behaviours among children occur as a result of aggression. Also, concerning the non-compliance, 34(76%) of the respondents which is the majority agreed to the fact that it is a common problem behaviour among their children. This finding supports earlier

research conducted by (Thompson, 2011) which revealed that the most common children's problem behaviour is that they do not follow directions from a teacher or caregiver but rather like to talk constantly with their peers and not to listen to a teacher or health professional, whilst 24% of them disagreed to the statement. Regarding hyperactivity in pre-school centres, a majority of the respondents 38(84.4%) agreed that their pre-schoolers exhibited such problem behaviour whilst 7(16%) respondents disagreed to the statement that hyperactivity was not a problem behaviour in their pre-school centres. This finding supports that of Tay& Sim (2008) that hyperactivity is a common problem behaviour complaint in children and is characterized by an increase in motor activity to a level that interferes with the child's functioning at school, at home or socially. Relating to destructiveness prevailing among children, a majority of 33(73%) respondent agreed to that statement, while twelve respondents being 26% disagreed.

The following themes emerged from the qualitative data collected, the themes were related to threatening and violent behaviour, refusal to take instruction, hyperactivity, wilful destruction of school properties (vandalism).

3.7 Threatening and Violent Behaviour

Among the themes which emerged from qualitative data was threatening and violent behaviour. According to the interview data, respondents were motivated to give the needed information about aggressive behaviour. They were of the view that children's aggression is characterized by a threatening attitude and has a serious impact on the classroom activity. Respondents were of the view that frightening behaviour among children breeds disruption during the learning process and waste instructional time. One of the respondents commented:

"In my classroom, I always see the children playing together. The children who are strong in the classroom are found fighting the young ones. They even threaten to beat the young ones who will come and tell me the teacher that some boy has beaten them. One girl took another girl's pencil and broke it. Afterward, she threatened to beat her if she decides to inform the teacher. So, when I saw the girl whose pencil has been broken crying and I called her to find out and she told me what the other girl has said." (ECT-5)

Interestingly, the data revealed that some respondents were of the view that children also display violence act when they are aggressive. They think that children were violent at any time they become aggressive. The respondents highlighted that, they felt aggrieved behaviour among children makes them violent even to the extent of damaging peers/ school item. One respondent said:

"As a teacher, any time I see children fighting one another, they end up destroy items in the classroom. One serious thing about such children is that, they become violent to the level that they damage classroom TLMs, push tables here and there and brake items." (ECT-4)

The forgoing comments suggest that; children become aggressive when violent. It could also be deduced from the data that, children exhibit frightening/threatening behaviour like young child kicks, bites or fights with other children, throw stones, run after another child when it comes to issues aggression.

3.8 Refusal to Take Instruction

Another major concern that appeared from the interview data was related to respondents experiencing children refused to take instruction.

Firstly, the data suggested that most of the respondents were of the view that children refused to obey or take instructions because they needed attention. Some begin to walk around instead of sitting and refused to submit the exercise books given to them by their teachers. A respondent shared her experience by saying that:

“Whenever I am teaching, I remind my children of the need to raise their hands before talking or answering a question. There is a boy called Kwame who is always found refusing instruction by talking and answering questions before I call someone to give the answer. This boy refuses to take every instruction I give in the classroom. Very often I shout at him or cane him.” (ECT-15)

The foregoing data presented, proposed that non-compliance behaviour is characterized by refusal to take instruction or follow rules. The data also suggested that children sometimes choose to ignore instructions given to them by their teacher in the classroom.

3.9 Hyperactivity (Excessive Activities)

From the interviewed data, another area which became known was excessive activity/restlessness. Primarily, the data suggested that most of the respondents met some form of hyperactivity because of the restless nature of the behaviour the children show at school. The data revealed that respondents sometimes expressed their frustrations they go through in handling children with hyperactive behaviour. Respondents also expressed their frustration that they had to keep eyes to monitor the children with the hyperactive condition since they always want to do something. A respondent shared her experience by saying that:

“As a teacher, I move around the various tables in classroom to see children are doing. Very often I see some children writing their classwork and within the next moment this same children are seen on a different table drumming and this drumming does not even relate to the exercise they have been given. In such a situation, I go closer to stops them from what they doing.” (ECT-15)

Another respondent commented:

"Hmm! One day, I was teaching at K.G 2. I saw that there was one young girl who was always shifting from one unfinished activity to another. Even though the whole class would be writing, she will be drawing. In another instance this girl will be writing and all of a sudden, she will move to a different table to snatch someone's pencil and move to another table to pick a crayon. This is not a good habit at all." (ECT-4)

The data presented indicated that, a child with hyperactivity shows excessive activities such as: difficulty to remain on seat, shifting from one unfinished activity to another. It also suggests that hyperactive children exhibit restless behaviour This affect classroom learning.

3.10 Intentional Destruction of Property (Vandalism)

Another major concern that appeared from the interview data was related to respondents experiencing the destruction of property within the classroom setting. Firstly, the data suggested that most of the respondents were unhappy because of the multiple destructive activities the children were engaged in. The data revealed that respondents sometimes destroy other children's items like pencil, books, erasers, pushing tables and chairs etc while teaching and learning were in progress. A respondent shared her experience by saying that:

"Most often, I hide behind the scenes with the intention of observing what will happen in my classroom Anytime I do that, I see a lot of things. Often, I will see that, one of the children will throw a blackboard ruler at another and it will fall on the ground and break. In another scenario, I will see two of the boys fighting one another and the one who will be beaten then moves to take anything belonging to the other boy and destroy it by hitting it on the floor. This damaging behaviour can happen even when the teacher is in the classroom." (ECT-8)

Furthermore, respondents also agreed that children who are engaged in destructive behaviour are found kicking and throwing things. They throw anything that they see within their environment. Some even go to the extent of throwing their school bags and other objects at peers who make them angry without considering what they have in their bags before throwing them at their peers. In this situation, the objects the children throw may be destroyed in the process. A respondent claimed that:

"During break periods at school, I move to see what children do. In the process I will see that, one of the girls will be hit by another and in respond the other girl will throw her leg to hit the food flask which is containing food and the food in the flask poured out of the flask. So, I go to the school canteen to buy rice and beans for that child to compensate her." (ECT-6)

Another respondent noted:

“At times, I see children kicking their launch bowls and throwing bags which has their food. Onetime in the classroom a child kicked someone’s bowl and the other boy destroyed his pencil by breaking them into pieces.” (ECT-11)

The data presented suggest that a considerable number of respondents were of the view that children with destructive behaviour tend to engage in deliberate activities such as destroying /damaging peers objects. The data further suggest that children with destructive behaviour could be seen to intentionally destroy property others.

Research Question Two: What are the classroom management strategies adopted to manage children’s problem behaviour in the selected pre-schools in the Effutu Municipality?

Table 2: Classroom management strategies adopted by the kindergarten teachers to manage children’s problem behaviour

Statement	Agree		Disagree	
	F	(%)	F	(%)
I use visual and verbal cue	40	88.9	5	11.1
I teach about the expected behaviours	41	91.1.	4	8.9
I give consistent and sound responses to rule violations	45	100	0	0.0
I provide individualized programming for more chronic behavioural difficulties	37	82.2	8	17.8
I make sure rule violations are addressed immediately and effectively	43	95.6	2	4.4
I ensure that individualized behavioural programs are instituted for children with more chronic behavioural difficulties	34	75.6	11	24.4
I make sure that quality teacher-student and peer relationships are encouraged	44	97.8	1	2.2
I use effective school-wide disciplinary practices such as reinforcement of good behaviour	44	97.8	1	2.2
I provide classroom-wide behaviour management strategies	45	100	0	0.0
I use effective instructional practices such as doing activities in turns	45	100	0	0.0
I practice problem-solving skills training	38	84.4.	7	15.6
I specially designed instruction and individualized behavioural intervention plans	38	84.4.	7	15.6
I use functional behaviour assessments	38	84.4.	7	15.6
I have designed behaviour intervention plans,	45	100	0	0.0
I have put in place Individualized Education Plans	35	77.8	10	22.2
I teach playground rules, routines, and desired behaviours	45	100	0	0.0
I develop general behaviour standards	39	86.7	6	13.3
I design individual behaviour change plans for children with significant behavioural difficulties	40	88.9	5	11.1
I use appropriate classroom arrangement practices	45	100	0	0.0
I have instituted reward and punishment systems	44	97.8	1	2.2
I have reduced transitional time	33	73.3	12	26.3
I practice active student involvement in creating and learning classroom/school behavioural norms	43	95.6	2	4.4

I provide a link of working with parents	42	93.3	3	6.7
I practice the creation of a community of caring and support	37	82.2	8	17.8
I provide a comprehensive program addressing the needs of children with problem behaviours	35	77.8	10	22.2

Source: Field data (2018).

Table 2 shows the description of respondents' responses to items relating to classroom management strategies. From the table, 40(89%) of the respondents agreed that they use visual and verbal cue as proactive interventions while a smaller number of the respondents 5(11%) disagreed with this statement. Almost all the respondents, 41(91%) agreed that they taught expected behaviours, while a minority of the respondents 4(9%) remarked they do not. Concerning consistent and sound responses to rule violations, all the respondents 45(100%) opted to agree to this assertion. This finding implies that all the teachers of the selected pre-schools consistently managed their children rule violations with a clear and concrete set of classroom rules. Meardor, (2017) argues that rules and expectations should be simple, straightforward and clear, covering the essential aspects of behaviour management. You must be fair and consistent no matter who the pupil is. Majority of the respondents 37(82%) agreed that they supplied individualized programmes for chronic behavioural difficulties while 8(18%) of the respondents disagreed to this statement. With regards to proactive interventions like rule violations, 43(96%) of the respondents agreed that they addressed them immediately and effectively, while 2(4%) respondents disagreed this statement. Most of the respondents numbering 34(76 %) agreed that individualized behavioural programs were instituted for children with chronic behavioural difficulties. A minority of the respondents totalling 11(24) of the respondents disagreed to this statement. Concerning quality teacher-student and peer relationships being encouraged, a total of 44(98%) respondents opted to agree while 1(2%) of the respondent disagreed to this statement. This finding implies that almost all the respondents had some amount of knowledge about the effect of good teacher-student and peer relationships and practised that in their respective early childhood centres.

Regarding positive behaviour support, a greater number of respondents, 44(98%) agreed to this assertion, only 1(2%) of the respondents disagreed to this assertion. Concerning classroom-wide behaviour management strategies, all the respondents totalling 45(100%) agreed to this statement. The implication here is that because of the nature of the children, the respondents use reinforcement to manage children's behaviour. Mostly, reinforcement was used to control children misbehaviours (Pettit, 2012; Farmer, Reinke, & Brooks, 2014). Considering doing activities in turns, all the respondents 45(100%) agreed that. Most of the respondent, 38(84%) agreed that they practice problem-solving skills training, while 7(16) of the respondents disagreed. Majority of the respondents, 38(84%) agreed that instruction and individualized behavioural intervention plans were designed as part of positive behaviour support strategy, 7(16%) of the respondents disagreed to this statement. Most of the respondents 38(84%) agreed to practice functional behaviour assessments, 7(16%) of the respondents

disagreed. Concerning behaviour intervention plans, a total number of 45(100%) respondents opted to agree with this assertion. This finding implies that the respondents adopted behaviour intervention plans such as changing the sitting arrangement of children and rearranging classroom to help manage children's problem behaviour. Findings revealed that changing a child's environment reduces the occurrence of the behaviour. This finding supports earlier research conducted by (Evans & Lovell, 2009; Fullerton & Guardino, 2010; Schilling & Schwartz, 2004) that the physical arrangement and features of the classroom environment, such as seating arrangements, lighting, and organization, can influence children' behaviour and attention to academic tasks. Many of the respondents 35(78%) agreed they practised individualized education plans while 10(22%) disagreed to this statement. All the respondents, 45(100%) responded that they taught playground rules, routines, and desired behaviours (Fullerton & Guardino).

With regards to comprehensive classroom management, it was revealed from the data that most of the respondents, 39(87%) agreed that they developed general behaviour standards while 13(13%) of the respondent did not. Also, majority of the respondents 40(89%) indicated that they had behaviour change plans for children with significant behavioural difficulties while a minority 5(11%) of the respondents asserted that they did not have any such plan. Furthermore, All the respondents 45(100%) indicated that they practised proper classroom arrangement. Majority of the respondents, 44(98%) agreed that they instituted reward and punishment systems as a comprehensive classroom management strategy, while 1(2%) of the respondents disagreed. A greater number of the respondents, 33(73%) agreed to reduce transitional time, 12(26%) of the respondents disagreed to the statement. The findings here revealed that the teachers had adequate knowledge about good classroom management techniques and applied them to reduce problem behaviour among the students. Researchers have investigated the relationship between the classroom environment, children behaviour and academic engagement. A well-organized classroom promotes good interaction between the teacher and children, reduce the probability that problem behaviour will occur (Martella, Nelson, & Marchchand-Martella, 2003)

Also, almost all the teachers in the selected schools, 43(96%) indicated that they actively involve their students in creating and learning classroom/school behavioural norms whilst a few 2(4%) of them said they did not involve them. With respondents providing a working link with parents, majority of them 42(93%) responded that they had workable links that helped them to closely work with the parents of their students whilst the minority 3(7%) rated that they did not have such link. Again, 37(82%) of the respondents asserted that they had created communities of caring and support for their learners while 8(18%) of them indicated that they had not. Finally, most of the respondents 35(78%) agreed to provide comprehensive programmes to address the needs of children with problem behaviours, while 10(22%) respondents disagreed to this statement. This result may mean that majority of the early childhood teachers did not impose rules and regulations regarding classroom and school acceptable behaviour on their students rather they actively involved them in the process. Also, a good number of

the respondents collaborated with parents of their students for the good upbringing of their students, provided conducive learning environments for managing problem behaviour among their learners.

Concerning the research question four, several themes emerged from the questionnaire and one-on-one interview. These themes were related to consistent and sound responses to rule violations, classroom-wide behaviour management strategies, effective instructional practices such as doing activities in turns, behaviour intervention plans, teaching playground rules, routines, and desired behaviours.

The following themes emerged from the qualitative data collected. The themes were related to a verbal warning, application of behaviour consequences, reward and punishment, classroom modification.

3.11 Verbal Warning

Verbal warning surfaced as one of the strategies during the one-one interview process. According to the interview data, verbal warning responses were used as major management strategies by the respondents. Most of the respondents emphasized that they always managed children rule violations with verbal warnings. One respondent expressed her consent that:

"I always position myself in such a way that anytime I am teaching I can see everyone's face. I mostly use simple verbal warning in response to the child who is misbehaving. If I do not warn the child who misbehaves, the others will do the same." (ECT-10)

Another respondent added:

"For me anytime a child goes against a rule in the classroom, I shout at him/ her or warn. Whenever I shout or warn child for doing the wrong thing, the rest become aware that, I am not comfortable with what their friend has done." (ECT-14)

On the contrary, a minority of the respondents argue that verbal warning alone may not be effective. Therefore, it will be more appropriate to apply the consequences of that behaviour. A respondent shared her view:

"As for me, whenever a child in my class misbehaves or fail to respect the rules in the classroom. I apply that behaviour consequences like time out or standing in front of the whole class. I do this to the extent that, that child will not do that again." (ECT-15)

Another respondent added:

"It is not enough to shout at the child or warn him/her verbally. In my classroom, some of the consequences of the behaviour is time out, you put your finger on your lips. So instead

of shouting, I will choose to enforce some of these consequences which will help me.” (ECT-11)

Inferring from the responses, it could be suggested that, most of the respondents use verbal warning to respond to children rule violation. It could also be deduced that minority respondents applied the consequences of the behaviour to deter the children. This affords the respondents some opportunity to control the children behaviour in the classroom. And this significantly helped academic activities.

3.12 Reward and Punishment

Another area of importance which came up during the interview schedule was reward and punishment. It appeared from the interview data that, respondents used reward and punishment to manage children behaviour. The interview data pointed out that, because of the nature of children, they reinforced reward and punishment as a means of correcting children behaviour problem on the spot. One respondent claimed that:

“Sometimes I reward children by giving them a token, sticker. Mostly I give them simple good marks, comments of praise. On the other hand, I punish children by informing their parents and discussing their behaviour with them. This ensures that the children do not disturb or misbehave in class again. I do this to discourage undesirable behaviours in them. And this contributed to the well-being of the children.” (ECT-1)

Nevertheless, other respondents highlighted that, apart from using reward as a management strategy, they were motivated to correct children misbehaviour on the spot. Respondents claimed that, although their roles as teachers were demanding, they were willing to do their best to help their children put up the desired behaviour. One of the respondents claimed that:

“Although sometimes teaching children gets tough, I always ensure that I keep eyes on the children. I try to do my best to keep my eye contact on them. I do that, so I can see the children who will be doing their own things in the classroom or those who will not be paying attention in class. I have seen that any moment I punish one of the children, the rest take caution.” (ECT-9)

On the contrary, a minority of the respondents believed that using reminders in the classroom help to control the children's behaviour. This reminder affords them the chance to manage the class well.

Another respondent said:

“Hmm, very often when I am teaching, and I see some of the children disturbing or doing something different from what I am doing, I remind them of the rules in the classroom. Sometimes, using reminders in the classroom helps a lot.” (ECT-12)

It could be inferred from the responses that, most of the respondents used reward and punishment to manage the children problem behaviour. Also, it could be deduced that other respondents instituted reminders in their classroom as a behaviour management strategy.

3.13 Changing Sitting/Seating Position and Rearrangement (Classroom Modification)

Concerning the behaviour intervention strategy, changing sitting(seating) position and rearrangement appeared as one of the subjects during the interview schedule.

It appeared from the data that, respondents practised changing the sitting position to help manage children's problem behaviour. The respondents highlighted that they were intrinsically driven both physically and psychologically to arrange the classroom to respond to children's misbehaviour. The respondents contended that this brought a change in the children environment thereby reducing the occurrence of the behaviour problem A respondent said:

"I always tell my children in the classroom that, where they sit in the classroom is not their permanent seat. So, if I see any child who is not paying full attention in class, though she would not be comfortable I change her seat, so she would be in front. From time to time if a child disturbs others when there is a group activity, I intend to change the sitting position and bring her chair closer to my table, so I can check her actions. This has helps me to check the child's behaviour progress as well." (ECT-10)

Also, a minority of the respondents complained that they use time out as a supportive strategy to help manage the class behaviour. The respondents claimed that any time they use time out, the children become sad but that has helped them in their classroom management process. One of the respondents commented:

"As for me, the strategy I use is time out. I always do that to make sure that the behaviour that are not helpful are minimized. Anytime I see a child disturbing, I allow that child to go to a place in the classroom, appointed as the time out or cool down area. My time out area is always away from the other children in the classroom. I give children five-minute best periods as time out. And after that child has returned, you will see hel/her as changed person." (ECT-15)

It could be deduced from the presentation that; respondents use strategies like changing the sitting position to manage classroom behaviours. Nevertheless, other respondents also adopted plans like time out to control children's problem behaviour. This strategy helped in managing the situation successfully.

3.14 Breaking Rules and Routines (Chunking)

Regarding the interview conducted, one other theme which came up was that respondents break rules and routines into steps. According to the interview data,

respondents practice breaking rules and routines down into smaller steps. This was used in teaching playground rules, routines, and desired behaviours. The interview data revealed that respondents made every effort to explain playground rules, routines to children using simple language to the children in the classroom. A respondent commented that:

"From time to time, when I enter the classroom, I help the children to set rules in the classroom. I also breaking down the rules and routine into smaller step for them to understand and follow. If I do not explain or break the rules into smaller step, they will do something to make me angry. Anytime I want my children to understand what I am teaching I have to break it into steps." (ECT-3)

It could be deduced from the data analysis that the majority of the respondents emphasized that they usually break rules and routines into smaller steps for children in the classroom. The data revealed that the essence of breaking the rules into smaller steps was to help control children behaviour.

The following key findings emerged from the study:

- 1) It emerged from the analysed data that, the common problem behaviour children displayed were aggression, non-compliance, hyperactivity, and destructiveness. The analysis revealed that children become violent and exhibit a threat when aggressive. The data further showed that children with non-compliance attitude refuse to take instruction/ follow rules. It was suggested that hyperactive children showed excessive activity. The analysed data further indicated that destructive children had the intent to plan deliberate activities or destruction of property (vandalism).
- 2) It emerged from the analysed data that consistent and sound responses to rule violations, classroom-wide behaviour management strategies, effective instructional practices such as doing activities in turns, behaviour intervention plans, teaching playground rules, routines, and desired behaviours were the dominated management strategies. The analysis suggested that verbal warning and application of behaviour consequences were used as consistent and sound responses to rule violations. The analysed data also revealed that respondents adopted reward and punishment as well as using reminders as classroom-wide behaviour management strategies. It was further revealed that respondents modified the classroom environment and implemented time out as a behaviour intervention plan. Additionally, it was discovered that respondents used breaking rules, routines, and down into smaller steps as strategies in teaching playground rules, routines, and desired behaviours.

4. Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn based on the findings;

1. The predominant type of children's problem behaviour was related to aggression, non-compliance, hyperactivity, destructiveness, threatening and violence, refuse to take instruction/ follow rules, and intentionally destruction of property. These behaviours affect their learning and classroom activity
2. The strategies adopted by the respondents were related to practising consistent and sound responses to rule violations, classroom-wide behaviour management strategies, effective instructional practices such as doing activities in turns, behaviour intervention plans, teaching playground rules, routines, and desired behaviours. The finding further revealed that other strategies were linked to verbal warning and application of behaviour consequences, reward and punishment as well as using reminders, changing sitting position (modification) of the classroom environment, time-out, breaking rules, routines, and down into smaller steps.

4.1 Recommendations of the Study

The following recommendations were drawn based on the findings of the study:

- 1) It is recommended that Effutu Metropolitan Assembly, Winneba Educational Directorate and the headteachers of the sampled schools organize behaviour guidance and outreach programmes for their teacher on the various types children problem behaviour and educate the teachers on the various aspects of the children behaviour and it corresponding demands. The above-mentioned institutions should organize field trips to preschool and institutions in the nation to expose teachers to the various early childhood working environment.
- 2) The researchers also recommended that the Effutu Metropolitan Assembly, Winneba Educational Directorate and the headteachers selected schools for the study should organise programmes on effective behaviour management strategies for respondents to equip them with proper management skills. Winneba Educational Directorate and the headteachers' selected schools for the study should institute policies which would protect the rights of children with problem behaviour. The Effutu Metropolitan Assembly, Winneba Educational Directorate and the headteachers of selected schools for the study should also provide facilities that would enable teachers better manage or cope with the situation.

4.2 Suggestions for Future Research

The study investigated the children's problem behaviour, factors responsible for the problem behaviour, effects and the management strategies adopted to control the problem behaviour among the selected schools in the Effutu municipality. It was, therefore, suggested that future studies should focus on increasing the sample of the study to include more respondents for the study. To conclude, future researchers should explore children's emotional problem disorder among various public schools.

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